

1 **Trait divergence in plant community assembly is generated by environmental factor**
2 **interactions**

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10
11 **ABSTRACT**

12 *Question:* What conditions drive trait divergence during community assembly through
13 environmental filtering, and why are some communities more trait-diverse than others?

14 *Methods:* An individual-based, stochastic, spatially explicit metacommunity simulation
15 model produced data on species traits, spatially autocorrelated, nested, feedback-generated
16 environmental factors, and resulting community composition. I quantified environmentally-
17 driven alpha trait divergence using the correlation $r(\mathbf{RE})$ to measure the relationship between
18 Rao functional diversity and environmental factors. Environmentally-driven beta trait
19 divergence was assessed through the correlation $r(\mathbf{VE})$, involving environmental factors and
20 the squared residuals (\mathbf{V}) of a second-order polynomial regression of community weighted
21 means on environmental factors (\mathbf{E}). Permutation tests, assuming independence between
22 traits and species composition, were used to establish the significance of $r(\mathbf{RE})$ and $r(\mathbf{VE})$.
23 Additionally, the method was applied to grassland and soil data collected in plots across
24 southern Brazil. Both simulated and real data were analysed at two spatial resolutions.

25 *Results:* Significant $r(\mathbf{VE})$ correlations were frequent with factor interactions incorporated in
26 community assembly simulations, while $r(\mathbf{VE})$ correlations mostly remained within expected
27 Type I error range when factor interactions were absent. $r(\mathbf{VE})$ was stronger than $r(\mathbf{RE})$ at a
28 finer spatial resolution and weaker than $r(\mathbf{RE})$ when smaller community units were combined
29 into larger units. $r(\mathbf{VE})$ for specific leaf area (SLA) was related to soil variables, likely due to
30 their interacting effects with total vegetation cover. When small plots were aggregated into
31 larger units, $r(\mathbf{VE})$ became non-significant, while $r(\mathbf{RE})$ increased.

32 *Conclusions:* Environmentally-driven trait divergence emerges during community assembly
33 due to interactions between factors affecting the selection of individuals based on their traits.
34 When the effects of these factors are spatially nested, including hidden, feedback-generated
35 ones, trait divergence arises at the beta or alpha dimension, depending on the scale of the
36 community units. This suggests that plant-to-plant positive or negative interactions, which
37 can feedback on environmental factors and generate heterogeneity, not necessarily lead to
38 trait divergence if these factors do not interact.

39

40 KEYWORDS

41 Environmentally-driven trait divergence, community assembly, environmental filtering,
42 factor interaction, simulation model, feedback-generated factors, grassland, plant community,
43 metacommunity

44

45 INTRODUCTION

46 As vegetation scientists, we analyse the spatial and temporal arrangement of plants to identify
47 patterns of plant species in communities and the associated environmental factors. These
48 factors may include variables reflecting available resources, site conditions, and disturbances
49 within community sites. Additionally, we investigate how plant communities impact
50 ecosystem functions and trophic levels. Despite the importance of predicting patterns, linking
51 them to underlying processes – often unobservable – is challenging and can only be inferred.
52 Knowledge of plant traits has become crucial in this context. Traits often exhibit convergence
53 patterns at the community level (e.g., Bruelheide et al., 2018; Carlucci et al., 2012), making
54 the filtering analogy appealing for explaining community assembly. According to this
55 analogy, plants with unsuitable trait values for local conditions are filtered out
56 (Hillerislambers et al., 2012; Keddy, 1992; Kraft et al., 2015). Consequently, the stronger the
57 filtering effect of an environmental factor, the more similar the selected plants within one
58 community will become (de Bello et al., 2009). Furthermore, changes between communities,
59 in terms of community-weighted means (CWM), may be related to gradients defined by this
60 filtering environmental factor (Pillar et al., 2009). However, we also observe that plants
61 coexisting within one community may diverge in their trait values, and the magnitude of such
62 divergence may be related to environmental factors (e.g. Carboni et al., 2014; Carlucci et al.,

63 2012), raising the questions of whether trait divergence in community assembly could arise
64 from environmental filtering and why some communities are more trait-diverse than others.

65 The prevailing theory explaining trait divergence is that competition is avoided through niche
66 differentiation (Chesson, 2000; Mayfield and Levine, 2010). According to coexistence
67 theory, we would expect species assembled in communities to be more distinct from each
68 other in terms of niche-relevant traits (i.e., limiting similarity) compared to those randomly
69 selected from the regional pool, especially when there are strong fitness inequalities between
70 species (Chesson, 2000; Mayfield and Levine, 2010). Although some empirical evidence
71 supports limiting similarity (e.g. Stubbs and Wilson, 2004; Wilson, 2007), the link between
72 limiting similarity and community assembly remains elusive (e.g. Price and Pärtel, 2013). In
73 any case, such trait divergence may vary between communities (Carboni et al., 2014; de
74 Bello et al., 2009). However, interactions between plants are often mediated by various
75 environmental factors that interacting plants modify at fine spatial and/or temporal scales.
76 These altered, feedback-generated environmental factors serve as selecting filters throughout
77 the dynamic process of community assembly and reassembly (Pillar et al., 2024).

78 Additionally, environmental factors altered by these plant-to-plant interactions might remain
79 hidden and not readily observable when they affect community assembly at a finer scale than
80 the resolution of the studied community units (Pillar et al., 2021).

81 An intriguing pattern observed in trait-based community analysis is the presence of trended
82 residuals around the predicted response when using linear models to relate community-
83 weighted mean (CWM) trait values to environmental factors (e.g., Figs. 4b,c in Bruelheide et
84 al., 2018; Figs. 2d, 4d in Laughlin et al., 2018). This suggests that the trait may also be
85 associated with other, hidden environmental factor(s) interacting with the environmental
86 gradient under consideration, implying that communities apparently under similar
87 environmental conditions may exhibit distinct CWM trait values. Consequently, the
88 magnitude of the trait residuals, whether positive or negative around the predicted CWM trait
89 values, may respond to the environmental factor that defines the gradient. Here, I define such
90 trended trait variation in the residuals, related to environmental factors, as *environmentally-*
91 *driven beta trait divergence*, and I define the trait variation within communities related to
92 environmental factors as *environmentally-driven alpha trait divergence*. However, for
93 brevity, I may henceforth refer to these simply as *beta trait divergence* and *alpha trait*
94 *divergence*. The challenge lies in understanding how such trait divergence can arise in

95 community assembly and how it may be perceived within or between communities
96 depending on the unit scale.

97 It can be demonstrated that trait divergence can be generated by environmental filtering
98 during community assembly. Figure 1 presents simple cases of hypothetical scenarios
99 illustrating the expected values of a trait (t_1) when species varying in the values of that trait
100 are selected (filtered) by two environmental factors (e_1 and e_2), either acting additively or
101 interacting. Let us assume that only factor e_1 can be measured, while factor e_2 is hidden and
102 not measurable. Thus, only factor e_1 can be used for the analysis of trait-environment
103 relationships. When the factors do not interact with each other in terms of their selection
104 effects on the trait (Figure 1a), the analysed residuals simply add noise to the prediction of t_1
105 based on e_1 and are not related to factor e_1 . A similar pattern of random noise is observed
106 when trait t_1 is selected by hidden factor e_2 only (Appendix S1).

107 Moving to a more complex scenario, Figure 1b, inspired by Cade and Noon (2003), illustrates
108 the expected trait values for trait t_1 as a function of both factors e_1 and e_2 and their
109 interaction. The interaction between factors can modify the strength and direction of one
110 factor's effect based on the other factor. Consequently, this can impact the variation of
111 expected trait values across communities that share similar environmental conditions given
112 by factor e_1 but vary regarding hidden factor e_2 . A similar funnel-shaped pattern is observed
113 when t_1 is selected only by the interaction of the two factors (Appendix S1). In the
114 community assembly process, the hidden factor modulates the selection effects of factor e_1
115 and, vice-versa, variation in factor e_1 modulates the effect of environmental heterogeneity
116 caused by hidden factor e_2 , resulting in an observable pattern of trait divergence in the
117 residuals that is associated with factor e_1 .

118 Furthermore, as the interacting factors simulated in Figure 1 are spatially nested in their
119 effects on the expected values of a trait, what is perceived as trait divergence between
120 communities (beta trait divergence) at finer scales becomes trait divergence within
121 communities (alpha trait divergence) when observed at coarser scales. In the case of non-
122 interacting factors (Figure 1c), trait variation within the larger units is unrelated to factor e_1 .
123 However, when the factors interact (Figure 1d), trait variation within the larger units is
124 affected by factor e_1 , provided the interacting factors are spatially nested in their effects (see
125 Figure S1f in Appendix S1 for a case in which the factors are not nested). Such beta and
126 alpha trait divergence are interconnected and scale-dependent when the interacting factors are

127 spatially nested, highlighting the need to assess them at defined spatial grains (analogously to
128 Carboni et al., 2014).

129 Here I present a conceptual and methodological framework to investigate patterns of trait
130 divergence in a metacommunity and gain a better understanding of why some plant
131 communities are more trait-diverse than others. Through a metacommunity simulation model,
132 I demonstrate that trait divergence patterns, both at the alpha and beta dimensions, can
133 emerge from environmental filtering driven by factors that are often hidden and feedback-
134 generated, and that interact in their effects on plant traits. Additionally, I describe a novel
135 method to measure and test beta trait divergence, and assess the accuracy and power of both
136 beta and alpha trait divergence using simulated data. Finally, I apply this method to analyse
137 grassland vegetation data.

138

139 METHODS

140 *Measuring environmentally-driven trait divergence*

141 I followed the steps outlined below, visually represented in Figure 2a. Matrix **W**
142 characterizes community sites based on species composition, while matrix **B** describes
143 species based on their traits. Normalizing matrix **W** by unit site totals and multiplying the
144 normalized **W** by **B** yielded matrix **T** containing the community-weighted mean (CWM) trait
145 values of the sites. This matrix operation is equivalent to the well-known equation for
146 computation of CWMs using scalar operations (see e.g. de Bello et al., 2021).

147 To measure environmentally-driven beta trait divergence, a linear regression was fitted for
148 each trait j on one or more environmental factors described in matrix **E** as predictors and the
149 t_{ij} values as response variable. Then, the squared residual v_{ij}^2 of each community i and trait j
150 was computed as

$$151 \quad v_{ij}^2 = (t_{ij} - \hat{t}_{ij})^2 \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

152 Where t_{ij} is the observed CWM trait value and \hat{t}_{ij} the CWM trait value predicted by the one
153 or more environmental factors. It can be demonstrated that v_{ij}^2 is equivalent to the difference
154 between community-weighted variance (CWV, Enquist et al., 2015) relative to \hat{t}_{ij} and
155 relative to t_{ij} (Appendix S2). To proceed with the analysis, the v_{ij}^2 values were compiled into
156 matrix **V**. More directly, matrix **V** can be computed as $\mathbf{V} = (\mathbf{T} - \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{E}'\mathbf{E})^{-1}\mathbf{E}'\mathbf{T})^{\circ 2}$, where $\circ 2$

157 indicates that such residuals are element-wise squared. For simplicity, the method is
 158 illustrated in Figure 2a by a simple linear regression of the CWM trait response on the
 159 environmental factor(s). However, this assumption may not hold true, particularly when the
 160 CWM trait values exhibit a non-linear response, such as a humped-back one. Therefore, to
 161 avoid possible misspecification of the model, a second-order polynomial regression was used
 162 in the analyses.

163 Beta trait divergence was measured by calculating the correlation $r(\mathbf{VE})$ between matrices \mathbf{V}
 164 and \mathbf{E} , as illustrated in Figure 2a. Since multiple traits and environmental factors can be
 165 involved, $r(\mathbf{VE})$ was defined as a matrix correlation. In this case, the Rd correlation (Omelka
 166 and Hudecová, 2013) was adopted. The Rd correlation is analogous to a Mantel correlation,
 167 but instead of the original distances, it is computed using the full matrix of Gower-centred
 168 distances. According to Omelka and Hudecová (2013), the Rd is advantageous in terms of
 169 power over the Mantel correlation, and in terms of computation demand compared to the
 170 PROTEST (Peres-Neto and Jackson, 2001) or the RV coefficient (Escoufier, 1973).

171 The significance of the correlation $r(\mathbf{VE})$ was assessed through a permutation approach under
 172 the null model assuming that the traits are unrelated to the species composition (Figure 2b).
 173 This involved permutation among the rows (species) of trait matrix \mathbf{B} while keeping species
 174 composition matrix \mathbf{W} constant. The \mathbf{T} , \mathbf{V} , and $r(\mathbf{VE})$ values were recomputed for each
 175 permutation, yielding a new $r(\mathbf{V}^0\mathbf{E})$. This process allowed testing the observed $r(\mathbf{VE})$ against
 176 the distribution of $r(\mathbf{V}^0\mathbf{E})$ values generated from the permutations. The probability (P -value)
 177 of finding equally extreme $r(\mathbf{VE})$ values under the null model was determined by the
 178 proportion of iterations in which $r(\mathbf{V}^0\mathbf{E})$ was larger than the observed $r(\mathbf{VE})$. This
 179 permutation approach follows a similar methodology to testing other trait-based correlations
 180 measured at the community level (Pillar et al., 2021, 2009; Pillar and Duarte, 2010) and
 181 addresses the concerns raised by Zeleny (2018). Moreover, by keeping the species
 182 composition matrix \mathbf{W} constant across permutations, any spatial or temporal autocorrelation
 183 present in the composition data becomes incorporated into the null model. This design
 184 ensures that the accuracy of the test remains robust against spatial or temporal
 185 autocorrelation.

186 Along with the P -values, a standardized effect size (SES) was computed based on the mean
 187 and standard deviation (*s.d.*) of the $r(\mathbf{V}^0\mathbf{E})$ values generated from the permutations:

$$188 \quad \text{SES } r(\mathbf{VE}) = \frac{r(\mathbf{VE}) - \overline{r(\mathbf{V}^0\mathbf{E})}}{\text{s.d. } r(\mathbf{V}^0\mathbf{E})} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

189 To measure alpha trait divergence, the correlation $r(\mathbf{RE})$ between Rao functional diversity
190 (matrix \mathbf{R}) and the environmental factors was computed (Figure 2a), and the corresponding
191 P -values and SES were obtained using an analogous permutation procedure (Figure 2b). The
192 correlation $r(\mathbf{RE})$ could be based on CWV, which is equivalent to Rao functional diversity
193 computed using squared trait distances between species (Champely and Chessel, 2002). Other
194 functional diversity metrics within communities could also be used (e.g. de Bello et al.,
195 2021).

196

197 *Type I error and power*

198 Is the test of the correlations $r(\mathbf{VE})$ and $r(\mathbf{RE})$ for measuring trait divergence reliable? To
199 address this question, I used a stochastic, individual-based, spatially explicit metacommunity
200 simulation model (Pillar et al., 2021), which was expanded to include environmental factors
201 capable of being feedback-generated. The objective was to assess the accuracy (Type I error)
202 of the test in correctly identifying the absence of trait divergence when the factors were not
203 interacting, and its power to detect trait divergence when it was expected due to the
204 interaction of driving factors in the selection of species based on their traits. Multiple data
205 sets were simulated, some with expectedly significant correlations $r(\mathbf{VE})$ and $r(\mathbf{RE})$, and
206 others without.

207 The metacommunity assembly model is rooted in the environmental filtering analogy. In trait
208 space, sites are described by expected trait values at the community level, while species
209 within a given species pool are described by their trait values (Figure 3a). Expected trait
210 values at the community level are determined by hypothetical functions describing trait-
211 environmental relationships. Assuming that propagules arrive at a site, the probability of
212 individuals of a particular species becoming part of the plant community depends on two
213 elements in this trait space, as explained in Figure 3b: (1) the importance of the trait for the
214 species' fitness, determined by the centre and slope parameters of a logistic function, and (2)
215 the proximity of the species trait value to the expected trait value at the site. Further details
216 on the metacommunity simulation model are provided in Appendix S3. Each metacommunity
217 data was analysed to evaluate alpha and beta trait divergence using the simulated matrices of
218 species composition, species traits and environmental factors.

219 To assess Type I error and power, two metacommunity simulation scenarios were considered.
220 These scenarios are hypothetical but constructed to resemble real cases. In scenario A, data

221 simulation was conducted using a species pool comprising 150 species described by three
222 traits (t_1 , t_2 , and t_n). The traits were uncorrelated, and each displayed independent responses
223 to environmental factors. Although traits in real data may be correlated with each other at the
224 species level (Díaz et al., 2016; Joswig et al., 2022), these correlations are also present at the
225 community level and in their responses to driving factors (Bruehlheide et al., 2018).
226 Consequently, simulations would not realistically capture this complexity if based on
227 correlated traits with independent responses to environmental factors. Therefore, each
228 metacommunity simulation generated a species-by-traits matrix, sampled randomly from a
229 population conforming to the specified uncorrelated trait structure (Pillar, 1999), as if
230 representing independent axes of trait variation.

231 For each metacommunity simulation, values for two environmental factors (e_1 and e_2) were
232 assigned to 1296 sites arranged on a 36 x 36 grid (as depicted in Figure S4 in Appendix S4).
233 Spatial autocorrelation was applied to factor e_1 by assigning identical random values to each
234 set of 4 x 4 adjacent 16 sites mapped onto the grid. Conversely, values of factor e_2 were
235 randomly assigned without spatial restrictions across the 1296 grid sites. Both factors, e_1 and
236 e_2 , were random values drawn from a normal distribution with a mean of zero and a unit
237 variance. With this grid design, the effects of e_2 on traits were nested within e_1 (as in Figure
238 1). The spatially autocorrelated factor (e_1) exhibited variability at a coarser grain (among
239 larger units), while factor e_2 was not autocorrelated and was set to vary within each larger
240 unit. The interaction value ($e_1 \times e_2$) for each site i was defined as the product $e_{2i}(e_{1i} -$
241 $\min(e_1))$, where $\min(e_1)$ represented the minimum value of factor e_1 across the sites.

242 Expected trait values at the sites were determined through linear response functions that
243 considered both environmental factors and their interaction. When a non-zero interaction
244 effect was specified in the simulation parameters, trait divergence was anticipated in the
245 generated data. The linear coefficients (slopes) for the effect of e_1 on t_1 ranged from zero to
246 0.6, and the effect of the interaction $e_1 \times e_2$ on t_1 also ranged from zero to 0.6. The effect of
247 e_2 on trait t_2 was set at -0.3, while trait t_n remained neutral with respect to the factors and
248 independent from the other traits. The maximum community size at each site was capped at
249 100 individuals, and each simulation ran for 100 years with 50 colonization/extinction trials
250 occurring at each community site per year.

251 For each combination of these parameters, 100 independent data sets, each comprising a
252 simulated metacommunity, were analysed to determine the P -values for alpha and beta trait
253 divergence measured by $r(\mathbf{RE})$ and $r(\mathbf{VE})$, respectively. To reflect a situation in which only

254 factor e1 was known and the other factor (e2) was unknown (hidden), both $r(\mathbf{RE})$ and $r(\mathbf{VE})$
255 were computed considering only factor e1. The analyses were conducted at two spatial
256 scales: one at a fine resolution using the 1296 simulated communities, and another at a coarse
257 resolution using 81 communities defined by pooling adjacent communities in a 4 x 4
258 configuration of rows and columns within the metacommunity grid. The analysis at the two
259 spatial scales aimed to assess whether the pooling of community units in such a nested spatial
260 structure would increase the power to detect alpha trait divergence ($r(\mathbf{RE})$), while decreasing
261 the power to detect beta trait divergence ($r(\mathbf{VE})$). The proportion of significant tests at an
262 alpha threshold of 0.05 indicated the Type I error (in the absence of an interaction effect) and
263 power (in the presence of a non-zero interaction effect specified in the simulation). For
264 further details regarding the simulation parameters, please refer to Appendix S4. In a slight
265 variation of scenario A, a reduced set of simulations also included a squared effect of e1 on
266 t1, which was set at -0.3. This was used to empirically test the method's sensitivity to model
267 misspecification in measuring beta trait divergence, as it is expected that t1 will exhibit a
268 strong humped-back response to e1 in this case.

269 Scenario B closely mirrored scenario A in terms of specified simulation parameters, with the
270 exception of the inclusion of a feedback effect from the developing communities to
271 environmental factor e2. In this case, the initial values of factor e2 were set to zero, and were
272 subsequently influenced by the effect of the CWM values for trait t1, which had a fixed linear
273 coefficient of -0.3 on factor e2. As the simulated metacommunity evolved, the values of
274 factor e2 were adjusted by the feedback effect, and the interaction values (e1 x e2) were
275 recalculated.

276

277 *Analysis of grassland data*

278 To test the method using real data, I analysed a dataset comprising 990 grassland plots
279 collected in south Brazil. The dataset included information on plant species presence-absence
280 and environmental variables (Menezes et al., 2022), as well as plant traits (Hoss et al., 2022).
281 The sampling design followed a nested structure, with 11 sites of 5 x 5 km selected at the
282 regional scale to represent various grassland types across six degrees of latitude. Within each
283 site, nine 250-m long contour transects were marked, and ten plots of 1 m² were surveyed
284 within each transect. Soil variables were described at the transect level, while variables such
285 as total vegetation cover, dung cover and rock cover were estimated at the plot level. The

286 plant traits measured for the species included specific leaf area (SLA), leaf area (LA), leaf
287 dry matter content (LDMC), and leaf nitrogen (LeafN), with missing trait values imputed (see
288 Hoss et al. 2022 for details). The trait data was natural log transformed prior to analysis.
289 Further information on the sampling design can be found in Appendix S5.

290 Initially, I analysed the data to identify the functional traits that best predicted community
291 patterns without knowledge of the underlying drivers. I employed the method proposed by
292 Pillar et al. (2021), which calculates the Rd matrix correlation (Omelka and Hudecová, 2013)
293 between two matrices: \mathbf{X} , representing a trait-based, fuzzy-weighted species composition
294 (Pillar et al., 2009), and \mathbf{Y} , representing a Beals-transformed species composition (Beals,
295 1984). Fuzzy-weighting is a trait-based transformation that fully captures the potential
296 community composition in terms of traits (Pillar et al., 2009), and it can also be
297 phylogenetically-based (Duarte et al., 2016; Pillar and Duarte, 2010). The resulting
298 correlation $r(\mathbf{XY})$ quantifies the extent to which the traits used for fuzzy-weighting reflect the
299 species co-occurrence patterns in \mathbf{Y} . Subsequently, the traits that yielded the highest
300 correlation $r(\mathbf{XY})$ were used to test for alpha and beta trait divergence ($r(\mathbf{RE})$ and $r(\mathbf{VE})$) in
301 the grassland data. The analysis was done at two spatial scales: one at the fine resolution of
302 the 990 plots, and another at the coarse resolution by pooling the plots within each 250-m
303 transect.

304 Principal Components Analysis (PCA) was applied to summarize the soil variables. The first
305 two principal axes were retained, which accounted for 35.6% and 28.6% of the total
306 standardized variance, respectively. The first axis primarily represented soil aluminium,
307 while the second axis reflected soil calcium. These two synthetic variables, referred to as
308 *soilPC_Al* and *soilPC_Ca*, were used in matrix \mathbf{E} to compute the correlations $r(\mathbf{VE})$ and
309 $r(\mathbf{RE})$. To visualize the compositional patterns, Principal Coordinates Analysis based on
310 Euclidean distances was applied to the Beals-transformed species composition matrix \mathbf{Y} of
311 plots by species.

312

313 RESULTS

314 *Type I error and power*

315 The results for simulation scenarios A (Figure 4) and B (Figure 5) were partially similar
316 regarding Type I and power. While in scenario A the spatially autocorrelated, nested
317 environmental structure in their effects on traits was predetermined and remained unchanged

318 throughout the simulation process, in the more complex scenario B the nested structure was
319 produced by the evolving plant communities.

320 The analysis of simulated data under scenario A, at both fine and coarse grains, showed that
321 beta trait divergence (Figure 4a) was seldom detected when there was no interaction between
322 factors e1 and e2 incorporated into the environmental filtering process during community
323 assembly. In the absence of factor interaction, the proportion of tests detecting beta trait
324 divergence for trait t1 was low and close to the designated alpha threshold for Type I error, as
325 expected, except for the cases with a higher main effect of factor e1 on trait t1, which
326 exhibited some Type I error inflation. Moreover, trait t2 and the neutral trait did not exhibit
327 any divergence, as the factor interaction had no influence on the simulation of community
328 assembly for these traits. Appendix S6 provides illustrative plots with cases of data generated
329 for different combinations of parameters.

330 Hence, under scenario A, the permutation test for the correlation $r(\mathbf{VE})$ mostly accurately
331 indicated the absence of beta trait divergence when it was not anticipated in the simulated
332 data. In contrast, when the interaction between the two factors was involved in community
333 assembly, beta trait divergence was frequently observed, indicating high power regardless of
334 the main effect of factor e1 on trait t1. However, this was the case only for fine-grain analysis
335 (unpooled sites). When sites were pooled (coarse-grain analysis), the power to detect beta
336 trait divergence was lower, particularly with an increased main effect of factor e1 on trait t1.
337 Furthermore, the results did not change substantially when first-order linear regression was
338 used instead of second-order polynomial regression to find the residuals in \mathbf{V} for computing
339 beta trait divergence by $r(\mathbf{VE})$ for both scenarios A and B (Appendix S7). However, when
340 simulated data under scenario A included a squared effect of e1 on t1, using second-order
341 polynomial regression maintained Type I error within expectation, while the first-order linear
342 regression resulted in inflated Type I error for the test measuring beta trait divergence
343 (Appendix S8).

344 Regarding alpha trait divergence measured by the correlation $r(\mathbf{RE})$ (Figure 4b), the analysis
345 with the same simulated data under scenario A indicated an acceptably low Type I error when
346 no factor interaction was incorporated into the community assembly process. Additionally,
347 alpha trait divergence was only detected with high power when the interaction effect was
348 strong and the sites were pooled. This outcome was expected, as the aggregation of fine-
349 grain, adjacent community units into larger ones at the same level of factor e1 incorporated

350 the trait divergence perceived between communities into the coarse-grain community units.
351 However, the decrease in power with the increased main effect of factor e1 on trait t1 was
352 much stronger for alpha trait divergence (Figure 4b) than for beta trait divergence (Figure 4a)
353 in both unpooled and pooled plots.

354 The analysis of simulated data in scenario B, which included feedback-generated variation in
355 factor e2, showed that when community assembly was affected by the interaction between
356 factors, the power to detect beta trait divergence using $r(\mathbf{VE})$ (Figure 5a) was high for trait t1,
357 particularly for fine grain analyses (unpooled plots). Additionally, Type I error remained
358 within the expected range for beta trait divergence for all traits, but only in coarse-grain
359 analyses (pooled plots). However, at the fine-grain level, with an increased main effect of
360 factor e1 on trait t1, Type I error was inflated, particularly for trait t2. As expected, the
361 neutral trait did not exhibit any divergence.

362 Regarding alpha trait divergence measured by $r(\mathbf{RE})$ (Figure 5b), the results indicate low
363 Type I error, especially in the coarse-grain analyses. Furthermore, power was higher at the
364 coarse-grain level but decreased with an increasing main effect of factor e1 on trait t1.

365

366 *Grassland data*

367 From the analysis, it was found that SLA ($r(\mathbf{XY}) = 0.346$, $P = 0.02$, $SES = 4.92$) and LDMC
368 ($r(\mathbf{XY}) = 0.193$, $P = 0.08$, $SES = 1.68$) were the traits that maximized the correlation $r(\mathbf{XY})$
369 when considered individually. The patterns observed from plotting the CWM traits and soil
370 variables on the ordination of the Beals-transformed species composition (refer to Appendix
371 S9) reflected the trait convergence component of $r(\mathbf{XY})$. For instance, highland grassland
372 communities exhibited higher CWMs values for LDMC and lower values for SLA, while
373 also showing higher AI content in the soil. This indicates the presence of a leaf-economics
374 spectrum at the community level along the LDMC-SLA axis, representing a range of nutrient
375 acquisition strategies from conservative to acquisitive.

376 Further analysis focused only on SLA, as Rd correlation $r(\mathbf{VE})$ measuring beta trait
377 divergence for SLA was low but significant, with a high standardized effect size ($r(\mathbf{VE}) =$
378 0.0384 , $P = 0.021$, $SES = 3.22$). In this case, the predictor variables used to compute the
379 residuals (\mathbf{V}) in a second-order polynomial regression were both *soilPC_Al* and *soilPC_Ca*,
380 with \mathbf{V} being a vector since only SLA was considered, and \mathbf{E} being bivariate.

381 Interaction plots (Figure 6) were used to identify other factors that generate beta trait
382 divergence through their interactions with soil variables. The diagram revealed that soil
383 aluminium-related variables (*SoilPC_Al*) had a negative effect on SLA. Interestingly, this
384 negative effect of *SoilPC_Al* on SLA was stronger (steeper slope) under low total vegetation
385 cover (represented by the light blue dashed line), and the interaction effect *SoilPC_Al* x
386 *VegCover* was significant in this case. Additionally, the effect of soil calcium-related
387 variables (*soilPC_Ca*) on SLA was stronger under high total vegetation cover (represented by
388 the solid line). It is worth noting that since the soil was described at the 250-m transects, the
389 10 1 m² plots within a given transect had the same scores for *SoilPC_Al* (and *SoilPC_Ca*),
390 but they varied in terms of total vegetation cover, which exhibited a clear trend. The
391 significant beta trait divergence confirmed this finding.

392 The effect of sampling unit size was also analysed. When the plots were pooled at the 99
393 250-m transects, beta trait divergence disappeared, yielding a non-significant *P*-value and
394 low effect size ($r(\mathbf{VE}) = 0.0959$, $P = 0.094$, $SES = 1.46$). However, the correlation $r(\mathbf{RE})$ for
395 alpha trait divergence was higher, though equally significant and with a weaker *SES*, at the
396 scale of 250-m transects ($r(\mathbf{RE}) = 0.377$, $P = 0.041$, $SES = 2.19$) compared to the scale of 1
397 m² plots ($r(\mathbf{RE}) = 0.176$, $P = 0.025$, $SES = 2.67$). In this case, $r(\mathbf{RE})$ represents the *Rd*
398 correlation between Rao entropy (a vector) and the environmental matrix with the two factors
399 (*SoilPC_Al* and *SoilPC_Ca*).

400

401 DISCUSSION

402 The results obtained from simulated data provide compelling evidence that certain plant
403 communities within a metacommunity exhibit higher trait diversity due to interactions
404 between environmental factors influencing the selection of plants based on their traits. This
405 phenomenon is here identified as environmentally-driven trait divergence. Furthermore, when
406 these factors are spatially nested in their effects on traits, including hidden, feedback-
407 generated factors, such trait divergence can arise between or within communities, depending
408 on the scale of the community units. It is important to consider that the filtering factors
409 influencing species composition based on traits are not solely external to the community,
410 such as coarse-scale climatic conditions. They also operate at a very fine scale, which may
411 reflect plant-to-plant interactions and their feedback on local resources, conditions and
412 disturbances at the direct neighbourhood of single individual plants, thereby enhancing

413 environmental heterogeneity at the scale of microsites (Hillerislambers et al., 2012; Jiang and
414 DeAngelis, 2013; Pillar et al., 2013, 2024).

415 In fact, both negative and positive plant-to-plant interactions are frequently mediated by a
416 range of environmental factors that interacting plants modify at fine spatial and/or temporal
417 scales. For instance, competing plants remove resources that then become more limiting for
418 each other, nurse plants add resources, or improve conditions, or provide anti-herbivory
419 protection that may benefit neighbours. Shorter, palatable plants attract grazers to the same
420 feeding station, which may also include not so palatable, taller plants, potentially reducing
421 competition for light. Additionally, allelopathic plants release substances that could hinder
422 the growth of neighbouring plants. It is worth noting that some environmental factors,
423 particularly those modified in these plant-to-plant interactions, remain hidden and not directly
424 observable. This is often the case when they are linked to unknown past conditions or when
425 they impact community assembly at a finer resolution than the grain size of the studied
426 community units (Pillar et al., 2021). Hence, trait divergence may arise from the interactions
427 between observable and such fine-scale hidden environmental factors filtering plants based
428 on their traits.

429 However, plant-to-plant interactions enhancing environmental heterogeneity would not
430 necessarily lead to environmentally-driven trait divergence if the factors involved do not
431 interact in their filtering effects. In the absence of factor interaction, environmental
432 heterogeneity caused by such feedback-generated hidden factors would produce within-
433 community trait variation unrelated to the measured factor, as depicted in Figures 1a and 5.
434 Interactions between ecological factors seem to be the rule in nature (e.g. Catford et al., 2022;
435 Spake et al., 2023). Therefore, this explanation for environmentally-driven trait divergence
436 appears to be more generalizable than considering plant competition and facilitation (de Bello
437 et al., 2021; Stubbs and Wilson, 2004; Wilson, 2007) or coexistence theory predictions
438 (Chesson, 2000; de Bello et al., 2021; Godoy et al., 2017; Hillerislambers et al., 2012;
439 Mayfield and Levine, 2010). Although the mechanism of limiting similarity, where
440 coexisting species avoid competition through niche differentiation, can be linked to feedback-
441 generated environmental heterogeneity and interpreted as environmental filtering taking place
442 at a very fine grain (see, e.g. Carboni et al., 2014), it is unlikely that environmentally-driven
443 trait divergence, as defined here, would arise by limiting similarity alone in the absence of
444 interaction between filtering factors.

445 The results with simulated data provide valuable insights into the reliability of detecting
446 alpha and beta trait divergence using correlations $r(\mathbf{RE})$ and $r(\mathbf{VE})$, respectively, along with
447 the proposed permutation test under the null model that assumes traits are unrelated to the
448 species composition. Additionally, a second-order polynomial regression should be employed
449 to determine the residuals \mathbf{V} needed for measuring beta trait divergence by the correlation
450 $r(\mathbf{VE})$. This approach reduces the risk of inflated Type I error when CWM trait values exhibit
451 non-linear responses to environmental factors.

452 Furthermore, analogous to Pillar et al. (2021), the simulated data revealed a suppression
453 effect in which the role of the two-factor interaction in generating trait divergence was
454 suppressed by the stronger main factor effect. Conversely, such interference between factors
455 and between traits may have influenced the Type I error. This suggests that these
456 interferences arise from how individual traits within the same plants are selected by different
457 factors and their interactions, which deserves further investigation. The assembly process
458 selects whole individuals based on traits that cannot be disentangled, and in reality these traits
459 are often non-independent and coordinated with each other, with relations restricted by trade-
460 offs (Díaz et al., 2016; Joswig et al., 2022). Thus, an unsuitable trait value can limit an
461 individual plant's success in a community site, although plants vary in terms of how critical a
462 trait is in this process. In relation to this, it is also worth further investigating the role of
463 feedback effects on community assembly, as represented in the more complex simulated
464 scenario B.

465 To enhance understanding, factors and traits in scenario B can be translated into potential real
466 counterparts, representing a plausible path model for grassland communities under grazing
467 (Figure 5c). In this hypothetical model, soil fertility exerts an expected positive effect on
468 SLA, and grazing intensity a negative effect on plant height. Furthermore, when interaction is
469 involved, the effect of soil fertility on SLA is modulated by grazing intensity. Due to the
470 positive interaction, this effect of soil fertility is stronger at higher grazing intensity and
471 weaker at lower grazing intensity. As the feedback effect of SLA on grazing intensity is
472 positive, communities exhibiting higher SLA tend to experience more intensive grazing
473 (Caram et al., 2023), creating heterogeneity in grazing intensity, which subsequently
474 influences the interaction. Consequently, the expected CWM for SLA becomes more variable
475 with higher soil fertility. Additionally, the positive effect of SLA on grazing intensity
476 negatively impacts plant height at the community level. However, these effects are not
477 entirely deterministic and depend on how critical the traits are for the fitness of each species

478 in the species pool (as seen in Figure 3b) and on the stochasticity inherent in the simulation
479 model. These hypothetical indirect effects of soil fertility on plant height, via the feedback
480 mechanism (Figure 5c), may explain the apparent inflated Type I error, i.e., the unexpectedly
481 high frequency of significant beta trait divergence for trait t2 (Figure 5a). Even in the absence
482 of an explicit interaction between soil fertility and grazing on plant height built into the
483 simulation model, the indirect effect via soil fertility -> SLA -> grazing -> height may mimic
484 the interaction effect, thus generating beta trait divergence for height in these simulations.

485 The analysis of the real grassland vegetation data in this study suggests that trait divergence
486 can be generated by the interaction between heterogeneous vegetation cover and soil
487 variables. In other words, the effect of vegetation cover heterogeneity on CWM SLA depends
488 on the level of soil variables, and vice-versa. Furthermore, some ecological factors driving
489 community assembly may be spatially nested, such as in the analysed data. This means that
490 what appears as alpha trait divergence at one spatial scale (grain) could be identified as beta
491 trait divergence at a finer scale, indicating that the alpha and beta dimensions of trait
492 divergence are interconnected. Beta trait divergence, as measured in this study, appears to be
493 a more widespread pattern than previously acknowledged and could likely be detected in
494 analyses conducted at global (e.g., Bruelheide et al., 2018) and regional/local scales (e.g.,
495 Laughlin et al., 2018).

496 In conclusion, the evidence strongly suggests that environmentally-driven trait divergence in
497 community assembly arises due to factors that interact in the selection of individuals based
498 on their traits. If these factors are spatially nested, potentially driven by feedback during
499 community development, such trait divergence can be observed at either the beta or alpha
500 dimensions, depending on the scale of the community units in such a heterogeneous
501 environment. However, it is essential to emphasize that such trait divergence, whether at the
502 beta or alpha level, is not solely a consequence of environmental heterogeneity. Instead, it
503 results from the interactive effects of various factors occurring in a heterogeneous
504 environment, leading to fine-scale trait variations among community sites.

505

506 DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

507 The metacommunity simulation model and the trait-based analyses, including evaluation of
508 power and Type I error, are implemented in the package SYNCOSA
509 (<http://ecoqua.ecologia.ufrgs.br/SYNCOSA.html>). The version used here is 2.12.34, which is

510 available at <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8376410>, along with the simulation
511 scripts necessary to reproduce the results. The grassland vegetation plots data are available in
512 sPlot (DOI will be informed at proof stage), while the plant traits and soil data (with
513 corresponding plot IDs) are deposited at <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10369008>.

514

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528

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673 Figure 1. Hypothetical examples illustrating expected values of a trait (t_1) in a set of
 674 simulated communities. The trait is selected (filtered) by two random environmental factors
 675 (e_1 and e_2) according to specified linear functions. In (a), trait t_1 is additively affected by
 676 factors e_1 and e_2 , and in (b), it is determined by both factors plus their interaction. The linear
 677 function slopes are shown in the insets. The red trendline represents the response of trait t_1
 678 modelled a posteriori with the generated data, using only factor e_1 as a predictor and ignoring
 679 factor e_2 and the interaction (greyed in the insets), as if e_2 were not measured. Note that the
 680 effect of simulated values of factor e_2 on trait t_1 was nested within the nesting factor e_1 . For
 681 this, each subset of 10 random values of e_2 in subunits corresponded to one identical random
 682 value of e_1 defining a nesting unit. That is, larger, nesting units contained ten subunits that
 683 did not vary for e_1 but did for e_2 . Random values were normally-distributed. The
 684 corresponding variance of trait t_1 within each of these nesting units and its observed response
 685 to factor e_1 are shown in graphs c-d.

690 Figure 2. General framework for measuring environmentally-driven beta and alpha trait
 691 divergence (a) and the corresponding permutation tests (b). In (a), the method for beta trait
 692 divergence begins with the computation of trait means at the community level (CWMs in
 693 matrix **T**), which are then regressed against factors in **E**. For each community *i* and trait *j*, v_{ij}^2
 694 is the squared deviation between the observed CWM and the predicted CWM trait value
 695 based on factors in **E**. For simplicity, a simple linear regression is depicted, but a polynomial
 696 linear regression of second order should be used by including the squared factor values as

697 additional columns in \mathbf{E} , as actual CWM trait responses often exhibit a humped-back shape.
698 In matrix notation, this is expressed as $\mathbf{V} = (\mathbf{T} - \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{E}'\mathbf{E})^{-1}\mathbf{E}'\mathbf{T})^{\circ 2}$, where $\circ 2$ indicates that such
699 residuals are element-wise squared. The matrix correlation between \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{E} measures
700 environmentally-driven beta trait divergence. In the depicted case, the residuals between
701 observed and predicted trait values increase with the increase of factor e1. Note that \mathbf{V} may
702 be a vector when just one trait is considered, or may be a matrix when the v^2_{ij} values are
703 computed for more than one trait taken alone. Additionally, the correlation between Rao
704 entropy in vector \mathbf{R} and \mathbf{E} measures environmentally-driven alpha trait divergence. In (b), the
705 rows (species) of trait matrix \mathbf{B} are permuted, and the derived measures (\mathbf{T}^0 , \mathbf{R}^0 , \mathbf{V}^0 , $r(\mathbf{R}^0\mathbf{E})$
706 and $r(\mathbf{V}^0\mathbf{E})$) are recomputed, keeping species composition matrix \mathbf{W} and environmental
707 matrix \mathbf{E} constant. After many iterations, the probabilities of finding $r(\mathbf{VE})$ values under the
708 null model are calculated as the frequency of permutation iterations in which $r(\mathbf{V}^0\mathbf{E})$ were not
709 smaller than observed $r(\mathbf{VE})$, divided by the number of iterations. The same permutation
710 procedure is used for $r(\mathbf{RE})$.

715 Figure 3. Example of a simulated trait space with nine sites, each described by expected trait
 716 values at the community level. Additionally, a pool of species (A-H) is mapped into the trait
 717 space based on their trait values. The expected trait values at each site were determined
 718 through linear functions representing trait responses to environment factors, similar to Figure
 719 1. Both (a) and (b) depict the same trait space, but in (b), the modelling framework for trait-
 720 based species selection (filtering) in community assembly simulation is illustrated for one site
 721 and two species within the same trait space. The probability (P_{surv}) that an individual of a
 722 given species (A or B), after dispersal, will become part of the plant community at one site is
 723 the product of the P_{surv} for the different traits. This depends on how critical the trait is for the
 724 species' fitness (defined by the centre and slope parameters of the logistic function) and how
 725 close it is (distance d_{hij} in trait space for species h) to the expected trait j value at site i .

726 (a)

727

728 (b)

729

730 (c)

Factor effects on traits:

731

732 Figure 4. Environmentally-driven trait divergence detected in simulated metacommunity data
733 considering the specified combinations of parameters under scenario A. Each graph in (a)
734 shows the proportions of significant beta trait divergence measured by the correlation $r(\mathbf{VE})$
735 with increasing linear coefficients for the effect of the interaction between environmental
736 factors e_1 and e_2 on trait t_1 built into the simulation. The same is shown in (b) for alpha trait
737 divergence measured by the correlation $r(\mathbf{RE})$. As shown in (c), the columns refer to the
738 effect of the factor e_1 on trait t_1 (ranging from 0 to 0.6). The rows refer to the scale of the
739 community units, whether the analysis considered the 1296 communities without pooling, or
740 with adjacent communities pooled into 81 communities. The other factor effects were
741 constant in every simulation. Trait t_n involved no selection effects. The red lines correspond
742 to trait t_1 , and the other lines to traits t_2 and t_n . Trait divergence is not expected in the
743 absence of factor interaction, thus the proportion of significant trait divergence indicates
744 Type I error, while for non-zero interaction it indicates the power of the permutation test for
745 $r(\mathbf{VE})$ and $r(\mathbf{RE})$. Each proportion was found after 100 simulations for each specified
746 combinations of parameters.

747 (a)

748

749 (b)

750

751 (c)

Factor effects on traits and feedback:

752

753 Figure 5. Environmentally-driven trait divergence detected in simulated metacommunity
754 data, considering the specified combinations of parameters under scenario B. Please refer to
755 the caption of Fig. 4, since the same explanations apply. However, in scenario B, the nested
756 structure was created by the evolving plant communities. As indicated in (c), the linear
757 coefficient of the feedback effect of CWM of trait t1 on factor e2 was set to 0.3, which
758 modified e2 as plant communities developed in the simulation process. In (c), factors and
759 traits were translated into possible real ones representing a plausible path model taking place
760 in grassland communities under grazing.

761

762

763 Figure 6. Interaction plot relating to SLA at the community level (*CWM_SLA*) (a) the first
 764 (*SoilPC_Al*) and (b) the second (*SoilPC_Ca*) principal component of the soil data, using total
 765 vegetation cover (*VegCover*) as the variable interacting with the soil variable. Note that the
 766 negative effect of variables related to soil aluminium on SLA was stronger under low total
 767 vegetation cover (the light blue dashed line), and the interaction effect *SoilPC_Al* x
 768 *VegCover* was significant. Also, the effect of the variables related to soil calcium on SLA
 769 was stronger under high total vegetation cover (the solid line).